

**TRANSIENT AND STEADY-STATE FORCED RESPONSE ANALYSIS OF MISTUNED
BLADED DISKS WITH MODAL PROPERTIES AND EXCITATION FORCES VARYING WITH
THE ROTATION SPEED**

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ABSTRACT

An effective method is developed for two major vibration regimes: (i) the steady-state periodic vibrations and (ii) transient vibrations. The analytical derivation of the expressions for analysis of both vibration regimes are made which allows: (i) accurate evaluation of the steady-state response for arbitrary varying loads and (ii) the effective transient response calculation. The methods use the large-scale finite element modeling of the bladed disks allowing the accurate description of the dynamic properties of the mistuned bladed disks. A reduced order modeling is applied, which is based on the modal properties of a large number of mistuned mode families. The effects of the varying rotation speed on the natural frequencies and mode shapes of a mistuned bladed disk and its effects on the amplitude and the spectral composition of the loading are considered. The history of the rotation speed variation is considered for the transient forced response analysis.

The methods are demonstrated on examples of simple test cases and realistic models of a turbine mistuned bladed disks. Numerical studies of the transient forced response and the amplitude amplification in mistuned bladed disks are performed when the resonance regimes are passed during gas-turbine engine acceleration or deceleration. The effects of different types of excitation force and mistuning on transient amplitude amplification are illustrated by a large number of computational results and comparative analyses. These results and analysis of transient forced response are shown on an example of a realistic mistuned bladed disk. The effect of the rate of the rotation speed variation on the amplification factors for forced response of

mistuned bladed disks is studied. Moreover, the history of the rotation speed variation and damping ratio of bladed disks on the forced response have been examined and the importance of considering the effects of the varying rotation speed on the modal properties is shown.

Keywords: Bladed disks, transient and periodic vibrations

1 INTRODUCTION

Mistuned bladed disks are dynamical systems with dense natural frequency spectra. The resonance regimes which are passed during variation of the engine rotation speeds affect the longevity of the engine determined by high cycle fatigue damages accumulated during engine operation. The analysis of steady-state and transient responses for mistuned bladed disks represents an interest in the gas-turbine engine industry for a long time, and the problem of analysis of mistuned bladed disks using high fidelity modeling is not fully solved yet.

The forced response prediction for mistuned bladed disks based on the large finite element models used in industrial applications faces several major challenges (Refs. [1]-[5]). One of them is the large size of finite element models which requires the development of effective and accurate reduced models to obtain accurate solutions in a practically acceptable time. Another important issue is the necessity to consider the effects caused by the rotation speed variation during acceleration and deceleration of an engine on modal characteristics of bladed disks, aerodynamic damping, and the excitation forces. The variation of gradients of temperature fields and stationary aerodynamic pressure fields together with the variation of the centrifugal force levels cause the variation of static stress

distributions over bladed disks and affect the modes shapes and natural frequencies of the bladed disks (Refs.[6]-[8]).

The bladed disks are subjected to transient vibrations when an engine accelerates or decelerates. The transient response analysis (Refs.[9]-[13]) has special importance when during the rotation speed variation resonance crossings are encountered, which is practically inevitable due to the dense bladed disk natural frequency and aerodynamic excitation spectrums and the rate of the rotation speed variation is large. The aerodynamic forces exciting on the bladed disks are complex functions on the time and spatial coordinates which vary with the rotation speed. In some cases, the analysis based on consideration of a mono-harmonic excitation by a selected engine order excitation component does not provide sufficiently accurate results. Therefore, the analysis needs to consider the complex excitation load fields, which is especially important for the case of the transient forced response prediction, although for the steady-state prediction the multi-harmonic character of the loads can be also significant.

Generally, the engine-order excitation can be further divided into two categories: (1) high-engine-order (HEO) excitation; (2) low-engine-order (LEO) excitation. Examples of the flow variations caused by the wakes of the upstream stage or potential pressure disturbances of the downstream stage as the source of the higher-order excitation (HEO) are reported (Refs. [14] and [15]). In addition, any loss of flow symmetry in the turbine causes low engine order excitation (LEO). LEO is especially important in turbines, which is usually caused by burner blockage, temperature variations emanating from the combustor and the throat width variations in the stator (Refs. [14] and [17]). The aerodynamic excitation is generally multi-harmonic and composed of HEO and LEO contributions (Refs.[18]).

Establishing reduced-order models (ROM) has been of great interest, particularly for large-scale finite element models of industrial mistuned bladed disks. Generally, ROMs can be categorized into two distinct groups: (1) component mode synthesis (CMS) methods (Refs. [19] and [20]); (2) system modes (SM) methods (Refs. [21]). To reduce the computational expense, the ROM method, based on the exact relationship between the tuned and the mistuned bladed disks, was adopted in our previous research efforts (Refs. [22]). However, the previous method of establishing ROMs had some limitations, because the impact of rotation speed was hardly considered when building ROMs. Because the modal properties of a bladed disk cannot be determined at each time step of the transient response calculation or at each rotation speed for the steady-state response evaluation due to the large size of the finite element models.

To make the steady-state and transient response analysis sufficiently computationally efficient to be practical, the modal properties need to be determined at a rather limited number of different rotation speeds and then be interpolated to obtain their values at any rotation speed and at any time instant. The interpolation of modal characteristics should be done for two types of data: (i) scalar values – such as natural frequencies and modal damping; (ii) a set of mode shape vectors resulting from

their excitation modal force values. The interpolation of the scalar values is straightforward and different approximation approaches can be applied for each of the modal scalar characteristics separately, e.g. as the spline approximation in (Ref.[12]).

While the interpolation of the scalar values is straightforward, the approximation of the mode shapes cannot be performed by conventional interpolation. To use the interpolated mode shapes in the forced response analysis, we need to preserve the basic properties of the mode shapes: their orthogonality and mass normalization. Both these properties are destroyed if the interpolation is performed. The method of mode shape interpolation preserving the orthogonality of ROMs for the aeroelastic analysis of aircraft flutter under changing of velocity number or angle of attack was developed (Refs. [23]-[25]). In Ref. [26], a method has been developed to ensure that the mass-normalization properties of mode shapes can be preserved during the interpolation and this method have been applied to analysis of vibrations in mistuned bladed disks.

In this paper methods for the analysis of two types of forced response in mistuned bladed disks are proposed: (i) a steady-state periodic forced response and (ii) a transient forced response. The methods are aimed at using large industrial-type finite element (FE) models. An effective approach is applied for the model reduction to ensure the practically acceptable computation time for both types of the considered vibration problems. The model reduction technique uses the modal characteristics of the tuned counterpart of the bladed disk and the dependency of the mode shapes and natural frequencies on the rotation speed is considered and described with high accuracy. Realistic excitation forces can be analysed with their spatial distribution over blades and time variation described and used in the analysis directly: without the mono- or multiharmonic representation. The equations of motion formulated for modal coordinates of periodic and transient problems are solved analytically for arbitrary periodic or transient loading.

The accuracy and efficiency of the methods are demonstrated using: (i) a simple lumped mass bladed disk model and (ii) a turbine bladed disk under the realistic and complex unsteady excitation.

2 ANALYSIS METHODS

2.1 General scheme of the method

The FE model of a tuned bladed disk sector is used to provide primary information about modal properties of a tuned bladed disk, which are used in the analysis of mistuning structures. The blade mistuning is then modeled by specially defined mistuning matrices simulating experimentally measured scatter of dynamic properties of blades.

A tuned bladed disk possesses the cyclic symmetry property: its geometry and other properties are unchanged by rotations about the cyclic symmetry axis by a certain angle. The motion equation of a mistuned bladed disk subjected to the periodic excitation can be written in the following general form:

$$\mathbf{M}\ddot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{C}(\Omega)\dot{\mathbf{u}}(t) + \mathbf{K}(\Omega)\mathbf{u}(t) = \mathbf{F}(t) \quad (1)$$

where $\mathbf{K}(\Omega) = \mathbf{K}_0(\Omega) + \delta\mathbf{K}(\Omega)$, $\mathbf{C}(\Omega) = \mathbf{C}_0(\Omega) + \delta\mathbf{C}(\Omega)$ and $\mathbf{M} = \mathbf{M}_0 + \delta\mathbf{M}$ are stiffness, damping, and mass matrix of a mistuned bladed disk respectively, which are expressed as a sum of the tuned matrices $\mathbf{K}_0(\Omega)$, $\mathbf{C}_0(\Omega)$, \mathbf{M}_0 and a perturbation matrices which model the blade mistuning properties: $\delta\mathbf{K}(\Omega)$, $\delta\mathbf{C}(\Omega)$, $\delta\mathbf{M}$; The T is the period of excitation force for a general case of a rotating bladed disk if it can be calculated as $T = 2\pi/\Omega$, where Ω is the rotation speed. $\mathbf{u}(t)$ is the vector of time-varying displacements for all nodes of the structure:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \{\mathbf{u}_1(t), \mathbf{u}_2(t), \dots, \mathbf{u}_N(t)\}^T \quad (2)$$

which is a matrix of the time response displacement for all nodes on the structure which consists of vectors of amplitudes for all nodes of the bladed disk: $\mathbf{u}_i(t)$, ($i=1,2,\dots,N$), where N is the total number of nodes used in the reduced model. The excitation forces of bladed disks take the form:

$$\mathbf{F}(t) = \{\mathbf{f}_1(t), \mathbf{f}_2(t), \dots, \mathbf{f}_N(t)\}^T \quad (3)$$

where the vector $\mathbf{f}_i(t)$, ($i=1,2,\dots,N$) is the periodic excitation forces applied to a node; the T is the period of the excitation forces.

The nodal displacements can be expanded over the mode shapes of a mistuned bladed disk:

$$\mathbf{u}(t) = \Phi(\Omega)\mathbf{y}(t) \quad (4)$$

where $\Phi(\Omega) = [\phi_1(\Omega), \phi_2(\Omega), \dots, \phi_{N_m}(\Omega)]$ is the matrix comprising the mistuned mode shapes vectors, $\phi_m(\Omega)$, ($m=1,2,\dots,N_m$), N_m is the total number of modes used in the reduced model, and $\mathbf{y}(t) = \{\mathbf{y}_1(t), \mathbf{y}_2(t), \dots, \mathbf{y}_{N_m}(t)\}^T$ is the vector of the modal displacements. Substituting Eq.(4) in Eq.(1) and multiplying from left by Φ^T we obtain:

$$\Phi^T(\Omega)\mathbf{M}\Phi(\Omega)\ddot{\mathbf{y}}(t) + \Phi^T(\Omega)\mathbf{C}(\Omega)\Phi(\Omega)\dot{\mathbf{y}}(t) + \Phi^T(\Omega)\mathbf{K}(\Omega)\Phi(\Omega)\mathbf{y}(t) = \Phi^T(\Omega)\mathbf{F}(t) \quad (5)$$

Due to the orthogonality and mass normalization of the mode shapes, the equations of motion formulated with respect to the modal displacements in Eq.(5) are decoupled. Thus, the forced response for each of j -th modal DOF can be determined from:

$$\ddot{y}_m(t) + 2\xi_m(\Omega)\omega_m(\Omega)\dot{y}_m(t) + \omega_m^2(\Omega)y_m(t) = g_m(t) \quad (6)$$

where $\xi_m(\Omega)$ and $\omega_m(\Omega)$ are the modal damping factors and the natural frequencies of mode shapes used in the modal expansion; $g_m(t)$ are modal forces.

This equation is solved analytically for any load and, as a result, the motion for any point at the bladed disk is calculated by using Eq.(4).

2.2 Determination of mistuned mode shapes

The finite element models of mistuned bladed disk comprise millions of DOFs and the calculation of their modal properties directly is unpractical due to the very large matrices required to be involved in the eigenproblem solution. Therefore, following the approach proposed in Ref.[22] the FE model of a tuned bladed disk sector is used to provide primary information about the modal properties of a bladed disk. The blade mistuning is then modeled by specially defined mistuning matrices simulating experimentally measured scatter of dynamic properties of blades and the significantly reduced eigenproblem is formulated based on the

A tuned bladed disk possesses the cyclic symmetry property: its geometry and other properties are unchanged by rotations about the cyclic symmetry axis by a certain angle. The mode shapes of a whole tuned bladed disk are obtained using the cyclic symmetry properties using a single bladed disk sector FE model. The tuned mode shapes are calculated separately for each nodal diameter (ND). The number of tuned mode shapes calculated for a family of modes calculated for each ND can be chosen significantly large to allow the accurate description of the mistuned mode shapes that participated in the forced response in the considered rotation speed range. The tuned mode shapes are collected in the matrix of tuned mode shapes, $\Phi_0(\Omega)(N \times m_s N_B)$:

for a case when the number of sectors is odd:

$$\Phi_0(\Omega) = \left[\Phi_0^0(\Omega) \mid \text{Re}(\Phi_0^1(\Omega)) \mid \text{Im}(\Phi_0^1(\Omega)) \mid \dots \mid \text{Re}(\Phi_0^{\frac{N_B}{2}}(\Omega)) \mid \text{Im}(\Phi_0^{\frac{N_B}{2}}(\Omega)) \right] \quad (7)$$

for a case when the number of sectors is even:

$$\Phi_0(\Omega) = \left[\Phi_0^0(\Omega) \mid \text{Re}(\Phi_0^1(\Omega)) \mid \text{Im}(\Phi_0^1(\Omega)) \mid \dots \mid \text{Im}(\Phi_0^{\frac{N_B}{2}-1}(\Omega)) \mid \Phi_0^{\frac{N_B}{2}}(\Omega) \right] \quad (8)$$

where $\Phi_0^{ND}(\Omega)(N \times m_s)$; ($ND = 0..N_B/2$) are matrices of mode shapes calculated for each ND; m_s is the number of modes calculated for each ND; N_B is the number of blades in the bladed disk analyzed. One can see that the dependency of the mode shapes on the rotation speed is allowed for. The calculation of the modal properties, i.e. mode shapes, $\Phi_0(\Omega)$ and natural frequencies, $\omega_{0m}(\Omega)$; $m=1..N_m$ for any rotation speed values is based on values of those accurately calculated for several rotation speeds in the frequency range of interest and the interpolation of mode shapes and natural frequencies between the accurate values.

The mode shapes are vectors, and the orthogonality and mass normalization properties of the whole set of vectors used in the analysis must be preserved. The conventional interpolation procedures performing the interpolation for individual components of the mode shape vectors (see Ref.[5]) destroy these properties of the mode shapes. Therefore, a special interpolation method developed by the authors in Ref.[26] is applied to ensure that the interpolated mode shapes preserve the orthonormality property. The natural frequencies are scalar values and their dependency on the rotation speed is approximated by usual spline approximations (see Figure 1).

FIGURE 1 THE NATURAL FREQUENCIES VARIED WITH ROTATION SPEED

The mode shapes and natural frequencies of a mistuned structure are calculated by extending the method developed in Ref.[26], to the case of modal properties varying with the rotation speed. In accordance with this method the eigenproblem for a mistuned structure:

$$[\mathbf{K}_0(\Omega) + \delta\mathbf{K}(\Omega)]\boldsymbol{\Phi}(\Omega) = [\mathbf{M}_0 + \delta\mathbf{M}]\boldsymbol{\Phi}(\Omega)\mathbf{A}(\Omega) \quad (9)$$

is solved using the expansion of the mistuned mode shapes, $\boldsymbol{\Phi}(\Omega)$, over the mode shapes of a tuned bladed disk, $\boldsymbol{\Phi}_0(\Omega)$:

$$\boldsymbol{\Phi}(\Omega) = \boldsymbol{\Phi}_0(\Omega)\mathbf{c}_\Phi(\Omega) \quad (10)$$

where $\mathbf{c}_\Phi(\Omega)$ is the vector of coefficients of mistuned mode shape expansion over the tuned mode shapes. Using this expression, the new reduced eigenproblem is formulated:

$$[\mathbf{A}_0 + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_0^T \delta\mathbf{K}\boldsymbol{\Phi}_0]\mathbf{c}_\Phi = [\mathbf{I} + \boldsymbol{\Phi}_0^T \delta\mathbf{M}\boldsymbol{\Phi}_0]\mathbf{c}_\Phi\mathbf{A} \quad (11)$$

The diagonal matrix of tuned structure eigenvalues, $\mathbf{A}_0 = \mathbf{A}_0(\Omega)$, is composed from the natural frequency values evaluated for the tuned bladed disk using the spline interpolation:

$$\mathbf{A}_0(\Omega) = \text{diag}(\omega_{01}^2(\Omega), \omega_{02}^2(\Omega), \dots, \omega_{0N_m}^2(\Omega)) \quad (12)$$

where the $\omega_{0m}(\Omega)$, ($m=1, 2, \dots, N_m$), are natural frequencies, which are dependent on the rotation speed. The computational expense of the eigenproblem given by Eq.(9) depends on the number of modes included in the analysis and this number can be chosen based on the expected forced response spectrum and the required accuracy of the calculations. This number is much

smaller than the size of the original FE model of a mistuned bladed disk. The solution of Eq.(11) gives us the coefficients of the mode shape expansion, $\mathbf{c}_\Phi(\Omega)$, and the eigenvalues of a mistuned structure, $\mathbf{A}(\Omega) = \text{diag}(\lambda_1(\Omega), \lambda_2(\Omega), \dots, \lambda_{N_m}(\Omega))$, which gives the natural frequencies of the mistuned structure: $\omega_j(\Omega) = \sqrt{\lambda_j(\Omega)}$, and the mode shapes of a mistuned bladed disk are evaluated at any rotation speed using Eq.(10).

2.3 Calculation of the modal force variation under steady-state conditions

The excitation force results from the non-uniform gas flow and is distributed over blade surfaces. The forces can be calculated by CFD solvers and we can assume that this function is known to us, therefore, we can determine the variation of the excitation force at any node of the finite element model of the bladed disk. The aerodynamic forces are varied with the operating regime of the gas-turbine engine and in the most general form can be presented in the stationary reference frame as a function of spatial coordinate and the rotation speed of the engine rotor:

$$f^s = f(z, r, \theta^s, \Omega) \quad (13)$$

where z and r are axial and radial coordinates and θ^s is the circumferential coordinate of the cylindrical coordinate system attached to the engine stator. The bladed disk vibrations are considered in the rotating reference frame and due to the variation of the load along the circumferential direction the forces excite vibrations:

$$f = f(z, r, \theta + \Omega t, \Omega) \quad (14)$$

where $\theta = \theta^s - \Omega t$ is the circumferential coordinate in the rotating reference frame, which is attached to the rotating bladed disk. The excitation forces can be evaluated for a set of nodes of the bladed disk finite element model with coordinates $\{z_j, r_j, \theta_j\}$ $j=1..N$. The number of such nodes in our method does not affect noticeably the calculation speed and the nodal aerodynamic forces are combined in a vector:

$$\mathbf{F}(\Omega, t) = \left\{ \begin{array}{l} f(z_1, r_1, \theta_1 + \Omega t, \Omega), f(z_2, r_2, \theta_2 + \Omega t, \Omega), \dots \\ f(z_N, r_N, \theta_N + \Omega t, \Omega) \end{array} \right\}^T \quad (15)$$

Then the variation of each j -th modal force over a period is calculated for each mode:

$$g_m(\Omega, t) = \phi_m^T(\Omega)\mathbf{F}(\Omega, t) \quad (16)$$

where the $g_m(\Omega, t)$, ($m=1, 2, \dots, N_m$) is the m -th modal force varying in time differently under the rotation speed- Ω ; the $\phi_m(\Omega)$ is the j -th mode shape which is dependent on the rotation speed due to variation of the centrifugal forces and the

temperature regime. It is convenient to introduce non-dimensional time, $\tau = t/T$ where τ varies from 0 to 1 over a vibration period: $T = 2\pi/\Omega$. This is convenient for the evaluation of the force only once for cases when the distribution of the aerodynamic forces over the bladed disk can be assumed not varying with the rotation speed, i.e. when the force can be expressed in the form

$$f = a(\Omega)b(z, r, \theta - \Omega t) = a(\Omega)b(z, r, \theta - 2\pi\tau) \quad (17)$$

The modal forces are calculated for a set of time instants over the vibration period, which is equal to the period of rotation. The time instants are selected to be uniformly distributed over the vibration period and the time step is selected to be small enough to capture the details of the force variation over the period:

$$g_m(\Omega, \tau_k) = \phi_m^T(\Omega)F(\Omega, \tau_k); \tau_k = k/N_T; k = 1..N_T \quad (18)$$

The spline approximation is then used for evaluation of the modal force at any time, τ within each of the interpolation interval $[\tau_k, \tau_{k+1}]$:

$$g_m^k(\Omega, \tau_k \leq \tau < \tau_{k+1}) = \sum_{j=0}^3 s_{mj}^k(\Omega) \tau^j \quad (19)$$

The coefficients of the spline approximation, $s_{m0}^k(\Omega), s_{m1}^k(\Omega), s_{m2}^k(\Omega), s_{m3}^k(\Omega)$ for force function $g_m(\Omega, \tau)$ can be calculated for the excitation force given by Eq.(17) only one time for the whole range of the excitation force and rotation speed variation. For the case when the rotation speed variation does not significantly affect the mode shapes of a mistuned bladed disk and the vector of excitation forces can be written as in Eq., the coefficients of the spline approximation can be calculated only one time for the whole range of the excitation force and rotation speed variation:

$$g_m^k(\Omega, \tau_k \leq \tau < \tau_{k+1}) = a(\Omega) \sum_{l=0}^3 s_{ml}^k \tau^l \quad (20)$$

where s_{ml}^k are the coefficients of the spline approximation for the calculated approximation for the function $\phi_m^T B(\tau)$ varying over the vibration period.

FIGURE 2 THE PERIODIC MODAL FORCE

2.4 Calculation of the modal force variation under transient conditions

The difference between transient conditions and steady state conditions is that the rotation speed varies with time. The variation of the rotation speed over time is defined by the needs of a pilot who operates the gas-turbine engine during a flight and the rotation speed can increase during the engine acceleration or decrease during deceleration. The function of the rotation speed variation is in practical conditions complex and we assume it to be known and approximate it by a piecewise linear function. In each of the time approximation interval $[t_h, t_{h+1}]$, the rotation speed over time can be represented in the form:

$$\Omega(t_h < t \leq t_{h+1}) = \Omega(t_h) + \alpha_h(t - t_h) \quad (21)$$

where the $\Omega(t_h)$ is the rotation speed at time t_h ; the α_h is the angular acceleration (or deceleration) within the interval which is a constant over the approximation interval. The bladed disk rotation, as a rigid body, is described by the rotation angle $\theta^{rot}(t)$. The value for this angle can be obtained for each h -th approximation interval:

$$\begin{aligned} \theta^{rot}(t) &= \int_{t_0}^t \Omega(\tau) d\tau = \sum_{j=1}^h \int_{t_{j-1}}^{t_j} \Omega(\tau) d\tau + \int_{t_h}^t \Omega(\tau) d\tau \\ &= \sum_{j=1}^h \left(\Omega(t_{j-1}) + \frac{\alpha_j \delta t_j}{2} \right) \delta t_j + \left(\Omega(t_h) + \frac{1}{2} \alpha_h \right) (t - t_h)^2 \end{aligned} \quad (22)$$

where $\delta t_j = t_j - t_{j-1}$ is the interval of j -th interpolation interval and t_h is the beginning of the considered h -th time interval. The variation of the circumferential coordinate for any j -th node of the FE bladed disk model over the whole history of loading can be then expressed as:

$$\theta_j(t) = \theta_j^s + \theta^{rot}(t) \quad (23)$$

The variable over time vector of nodal forces $F(t)$ is again composed from the forces applied to the nodes of the bladed disk finite element model. This vector is evaluated from Eq.(13) with allowing for the dependency of the rotation speed on the time together with the time dependency of the circumferential coordinate in the rotating reference frame:

$$F(t) = \left\{ f(z_1, r_1, \theta_1(t), \Omega(t)), f(z_2, r_2, \theta_2(t), \Omega(t)), \dots, f(z_N, r_N, \theta_N(t), \Omega(t)) \right\} \quad (24)$$

The modal forces are calculated as a function of time:

$$g_m(t) = \phi_m^T(\Omega(t)) F(t) \quad (25)$$

In contrast to the case of periodic response analysis where the modal forces are evaluated over a single vibration period, for the case of transient response analysis the modal forces have to be calculated over the whole history of loading.

The evaluation of the scalar products of the vector of excitation forces and the vector of modal displacements is time-consuming and such evaluation is performed for a relatively small number of points over the rotation speed range in which we consider the transient vibrations (see FIGURE 3). Then the spline approximation is applied to calculate the modal forces at any time:

$$g_m(t_k < t \leq t_{k+1}) = \sum_{j=0}^3 s_{mj}^k (t - t_k)^j \quad (26)$$

where s_{mj}^k ($j=0..3$) are the coefficients of the cubic spline approximation polynomial.

FIGURE 3 THE TRANSIENT MODAL FORCE

2.5 Analytical solution of the equation for the case of steady state response

The periodic solution of the equation of motion is obtained after the periodicity conditions are applied: $y_m(t) = y_m(t+T)$ and $\dot{y}_m(t) = \dot{y}_m(t+T)$, which gives us the expression for the steady-state forced response. The expression for periodic solution in the non-dimensional time, τ , takes the form:

$$y_m(\tau) = \frac{T e^{-h_m T \tau}}{\tilde{\omega}_m} \left[(C_s + \tilde{A}_c(\tau)) \sin \hat{\omega}_m \tau + (C_c - \tilde{A}_s(\tau)) \cos \hat{\omega}_m \tau \right] \quad (27)$$

where

$$h_m = \xi_m \omega_m; \quad \hat{h}_m = h_m T; \quad \tilde{\omega}_m = \sqrt{\omega_m^2 - h_m^2}; \quad \hat{\omega}_m = T \tilde{\omega}_m \quad (28)$$

$$\begin{aligned} A_c(\tau) &= \int_0^\tau g_m(\eta) e^{-\hat{h}_m \eta} \cos(\hat{\omega}_m \eta) d\eta; \\ A_s(\tau) &= \int_0^\tau g_m(\eta) e^{-\hat{h}_m \eta} \sin(\hat{\omega}_m \eta) d\eta \end{aligned} \quad (29)$$

$$C_c = \frac{e^{\hat{h}_m} [A_c(T) \sin \hat{\omega}_m - A_s(T) \cos \hat{\omega}_m] + A_s(T)}{1 - 2e^{\hat{h}_m} \cos \hat{\omega}_m + e^{2\hat{h}_m}} \quad (30)$$

$$C_s = \frac{e^{\hat{h}_m} [A_c(T) \cos \hat{\omega}_m + A_s(T) \sin \hat{\omega}_m] - A_c(T)}{1 - 2e^{\hat{h}_m} \cos \hat{\omega}_m + e^{2\hat{h}_m}} \quad (31)$$

The function $g_m(\tau)$ is provided over the period of vibration by the cubic spline approximation given by Eq(19) and the coefficients of the spline are determined by the table of the values provided. The substitution of the spline approximation in Eq.(29) allows analytical evaluation for these integrals:

$$A_c(\tau_k \leq \tau < \tau_{k+1}) = \sum_{h=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l=1}^4 s_{ml}^h J_{ml}^h(\tau_h) + \sum_{l=1}^4 s_{ml}^k J_{ml}^k(\tau) \quad (32)$$

$$A_s(\tau_k \leq \tau < \tau_{k+1}) = \sum_{h=1}^{k-1} \sum_{l=1}^4 s_{ml}^h I_{ml}^h(\tau_h) + \sum_{l=1}^4 s_{ml}^k I_{ml}^k(\tau) \quad (33)$$

where

$$J_{ml}^k(\tau) = \int_{\tau_k}^{\tau} \eta^l e^{\hat{h}_m \eta} \cos(\hat{\omega}_m \eta) d\eta; \quad I_{ml}^k(\tau) = \int_{\tau_k}^{\tau} \eta^l e^{\hat{h}_m \eta} \sin(\hat{\omega}_m \eta) d\eta \quad (34)$$

The analytical expressions for these integrals have been derived which ensure high speed and accuracy of the calculations.

2.6 Analytical solution of the equation for the case of transient response

The differential equation of a single DOF system that is exposed to excitation can be written as where the underline indicates complex variables. Applying initial conditions, the solution of the equation of motion for each modal coordinate involved in the expansion given by Eq.(6) can be obtained as:

$$y_m(t) = \tilde{y}_m(t) + \frac{1}{\tilde{\omega}_m} \int_{t_0}^t g_m(\tau) e^{-\hat{h}_m(t-\tau)} \sin(\tilde{\omega}_m t - \tilde{\omega}_m \tau) d\tau \quad (35)$$

where:

$$\tilde{y}_m(t) = \frac{e^{-\hat{h}_m(t-t_0)}}{\tilde{\omega}_m} \left(y_m^0 \tilde{\omega}_m \cos(\tilde{\omega}_m(t-t_0)) + (\dot{y}_m^0 + h_m y_m^0) \sin(\tilde{\omega}_m(t-t_0)) \right) \quad (36)$$

is the term that is dependent on the initial conditions formulated for modal coordinate, y_m^0 , and modal velocity, \dot{y}_m^0 . The integral in Eq.(35) is taken analytically for each interval of the spline interpolation used for the modal forces, $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$ given by Eq.(26). Then the expression for the transient modal amplitude function evaluated for interval $[t_k, t_{k+1}]$ takes the form:

$$y_m(t) = \tilde{y}_m(t) + \frac{1}{\tilde{\omega}_m} \sum_{l=0}^3 s_{ml}^k B_l^s(t) \quad (37)$$

where

$$B_j^s(t) = e^{-\hat{h}_m t} \int_{t_k}^t (\tau - t_k)^j e^{\hat{h}_m \tau} \sin(\tilde{\omega}_m(t-\tau)) d\tau \quad (38)$$

$$B_j^c(t) = e^{-h_m t} \int_{t_k}^t (\tau - t_k)^j e^{h_m \tau} \cos(\tilde{\omega}_m(t - \tau)) d\tau \quad (39)$$

The analytical expressions for these integrals have been derived.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Verification of the method using a 6-degree-of-freedom structures

To study the numerical properties of the methods developed for analysis of periodic and transient forced response and to verify their implementation in the computer codes a simple lumped mass model shown in FIGURE 4 is considered. The traveling wave excitation force is applied and the distribution of the excitation force along the circumferential coordinate is shown in FIGURE 5.

FIGURE 4 A SIMPLE LUMPED MASS MODEL

FIGURE 5 THE VARIATION OF THE TRAVELING WAVE EXCITATION FORCE

The mistuning is modelled by mass scatter and the mistuning pattern is shown in FIGURE 6.

FIGURE 6 THE MASS MISTUNING PATTERN

For the steady-state periodic response three methods have been used: 1) direct integration by Runge-Kutta method; 2) frequency domain method developed in Ref.[22] and 3) the new method proposed in this paper. In the new method the force shown in FIGURE 5 is described by spline approximation using 200 points uniformly distributed over the bladed disk circumference. The method developed in Ref.[22] and Runge-Kutta method use Fourier series for expansion of the periodic force function. For these two methods cases of 10 and 100 harmonics used in the Fourier expansion are assessed. In the directed integration by Runge-Kutta method the convergence of the vibration process to periodic steady-state response was achieved.

The steady-state maximum amplitudes calculated by the three methods are compared as shown in FIGURE 7. For Runge-Kutta and Ref.[22] methods 100 excitation force harmonics are used for this calculation. The results show that the results of the three methods are practically identical. The computation time of these methods are shown in TABLE 1. It can be found that the new method has higher efficiency when the accuracy of excitation force description requires large number of harmonics.

FIGURE 7 COMPARISON OF THE MAXIMUM AMPLITUDE CALCULATED BY THREE METHODS

TABLE 1 COMPUTING TIME UNDER DIFFERENT TOTAL NUMBER OF HARMONIC EXCITATION

The total number of harmonic	Runge-Kutta method	Frequency-domain method ([22])	New method
10	1103s	0.31s	0.34s
100	4203s	3.09s	

The numerical methods used for comparison in the transient analysis are: (1) direct integration by Runge-Kutta method; (2) the method using Fourier series expansion to describe the accelerated traveling wave excitation, which is developed in our previous paper in Ref. [12] - this method requires the superposition of transient responses under all of the variable single-harmonic excitation, which is suitable for the

case with less order; (3) the method proposed in this paper for transient response analysis.

The transient maximum amplitude envelope calculated by the three methods are compared as shown in FIGURE 8 for the mistuned bladed disk.

FIGURE 8 COMPARISON OF THE MAXIMUM AMPLITUDE CALCULATED BY THREE METHODS

The transient response envelopes of the three methods are similar. The calculation time of the three transient methods is compared in TABLE 2. It is seen that the new transient analysis method proposed in this paper has high efficiency, especially when the excitation function is complex and requires inclusion of many excitation harmonics.

TABLE 2 COMPUTING TIME UNDER DIFFERENT TOTAL NUMBER OF TRANSIENT EXCITATION

The total number of harmonic	Runge-Kutta method	Variable multiharmonic excitation ([12])	New method
10	425s	18.45s	54.64s
100	1783s	191.63s	

3.2 The model of a realistic bladed disk

A turbine bladed disk, comprising 86 sectors, was considered to demonstrate the efficiency of the developed method and to study the mistuning effects on forced vibration responses of bladed disks. The three-dimensional finite element model used in the analysis is shown in FIGURE 9. The whole model comprises about 14,701,000 degrees of freedom (DOFs) and a sector model has 171,000 DOFs. The blade-disk root joints are assumed fully stuck to consider linear vibrations. The damping resulting from structural and aerodynamic energy dissipation is modeled by modal damping factors provided for all modes involved in the mistuning bladed disk modeling.

FIGURE 9 THE BLADED DISK MODEL: A) A WHOLE BLADED DISK; B) A SECTOR

The tuned natural frequencies and mode shapes of the bladed disk were obtained using a sector model for all possible values of nodal diameters (ND) in this disk, i.e. from 0 to 43. The dependencies of natural frequencies on the number of NDs are plotted in FIGURE 10 where first 10 natural frequencies are shown. In the calculation of the mistuned reduced bladed disk model these first 10 modes of the tuned bladed disk are used for all possible nodal diameter numbers from 0 to 43. Each of the natural frequency of modes with nodal diameters numbers from 1 to 42 corresponds to two mode shapes. Therefore, the total number of mode shapes used in the reduced modal model of the mistuned bladed disk is 860.

The blade mistuning is modeled by attaching a set of lumped masses distributed uniformly over the blade surface, following the approach developed in Ref.[27]. The mass values are selected for each blade differently to describe the blade mistuning. For the mistuned bladed disk, random frequency mistuning pattern is generated with the maximum blade frequency mistuning 5% as shown in FIGURE 11.

FIGURE 10 NATURAL TUNED BLADED DISK FREQUENCIES

FIGURE 11 A RANDOMLY GENERATED BLADE MISTUNING PATTERN

3.3 Bladed disk excitation forces

For the blade disks, the unsteady excitation force distribution on the different nodes of the blade surface is different. Different spans are selected for detailed description of the forces distribution along blade length, namely: at 30% , 50% and 80% bladed length as shown in FIGURE 12.

FIGURE 12 LOCATIONS OF SPANS WHERE EXCITATION FORCES ARE APPLIED

FIGURE 13 THE EXCITATION FORCES FOR SELECTED NODES: A) IN TIME DOMAIN; B) IN FREQUENCY DOMAIN;

The examples of the periodic complex excitation forces applied at 3 nodes of blade surface are shown in FIGURE 13a, whose chord-wise location is 0.2 and span location is 30%, 50% and 80% respectively. The variations of the forces over the circumferential coordinate are taken from Ref.[18], where the periodic complex excitation force comprising HEO and the LEO are present. The harmonic composition of the forces is shown in FIGURE 13b. The number of the vanes in front of the rotating blade disks is 25. The contribution of the vanes is evident by significant contribution of 25th harmonic. The amplitudes of 50th, 75th, 100th and higher harmonics are significantly smaller than the amplitude of 25th harmonics. The low order harmonics from 1 to 10 are also clearly visible.

3.4 Analysis of periodic and transient forced response with variable modal characteristics

The developed method for description of dependency of the modal characteristics on rotation speed (Ref.[26]) has been applied to the turbine bladed disk. The natural frequencies and the mode shapes of the tuned bladed disk have been calculated using finite element sector model at 9 different rotation speeds: 0, 50, 100, 150, 200, 250, 300, 350 and 400Hz. The example of the dependency natural frequencies calculated for each nodal diameter for first family of modes on the rotational speed is shown in FIGURE 14. We can observe significant increase of natural frequencies with the rotation speed: for example, the natural frequency of 43ND mode increases from 1280Hz to 1600Hz which constitute about 25%.

The importance of accurate modelling of the dependency of modal characteristics on rotation speed was assessed by comparison of the results of analysis of the bladed disk obtained by our method (Ref. [26]) with two other approaches: (i) when the dependency of modal properties on rotation speed is ignored and (ii) when only dependency of the natural frequencies is allowed for. For the case with fixed modal properties, the natural frequencies and mode shapes were evaluated at rotation speed 0Hz.

The comparison of results obtained by these three approaches for a case of steady-state vibrations are shown in FIGURE 15 for tuned and mistuned bladed disks.

FIGURE 14 EFFECT OF ROTATION SPEED ON NATURAL FREQUENCY: 1ST FAMILY OF MODES

FIGURE 15 INFLUENCE OF VARIABLE MODAL PROPERTIES ON STEADY-STATE RESPONSE : A) TUNED; B) MISTUNED

The damping ratio of all systems is assumed 0.01, and all the responses are normalized by the maximum amplitudes obtained for the tuned bladed disk. The calculated forced responses obtained by these 3 ways of modelling are significantly different in some frequency ranges. For example, the resonance speed of the maximum response of the tuned bladed disk increases from 317Hz to 330Hz when the modal properties are accurately described, while the resonance speed of the maximum response of the mistuned bladed disk increases from 313Hz to 325Hz. The response levels differ significantly outside of the resonance regions.

In FIGURE 16 the maximum transient forced response is shown for tuned and mistuned bladed disk calculated for the case when the rate of the rotation speed variation is 20Hz/s. It is evident the importance of the accurate model property modelling for the analysis of transient vibrations.

3.5 Effects of damping and rotor acceleration on the transient response

The effect of the rate of the rotation speed variation on the amplification factors for the forced response of mistuned bladed disks has been studied. For both tuned and mistuned bladed disks, the steady state response amplitudes and the transient response amplitudes, are analyzed in this section. The considered damping ratios are 0.01, 0.005, 0.003 and the rotation accelerations of the turbine bladed disk are: 1, 10 and 20 Hz/s.

FIGURE 16 TRANSIENT RESPONSE FOR DIFFERENT LEVELS OF MODELLING OF VARIABLE MODAL PROPERTIES: A) TUNED; B) MISTUNED

FIGURE 17 compares the steady-state response amplitude and the envelope of transient response displacements for the damping ratio of 0.003 assumed for all modes considered in the reduced modal model. The results are shown for cases of the tuned bladed disk (FIGURE 17a) and mistuned bladed disk (FIGURE 17b). The plotted forced responses are normalized by the value of the maximum steady-state response amplitude of the tuned bladed disks found in the considered rotation speed range. The normalized amplitude of the mistuning blade disks is 2.1 for steady-state vibrations at the rotation speed of nearly 325Hz. The rotor acceleration requires the consideration of the transient response and the effect of the acceleration not only resonance peak amplitudes but also the response rather far from the resonance frequency.

The dependency of the amplification factors for tuned and mistuned bladed disks on the rotation speed acceleration is illustrated in FIGURE 18. The study has been made for three levels of damping: 0.01, 0.005 and 0.003. The shown here resonance amplitudes are the maximum values of the envelope curve of transient response displacements, normalized by the maximum steady-state response of the tuned bladed disks with the damping. The normalized amplitude of the mistuned bladed disk for steady-state vibration is close to 2.1 for damping ratio 0.005 and 0.003, and 2.05 – for damping ratio 0.01.

FIGURE 17 THE AMPLITUDES OF STEADY-STATE AND TRANSIENT RESPONSES: A) TUNED; B) MISTUNED

FIGURE 18 EFFECTS OF THE ROTATION SPEED VARIATION RATE AND DAMPING RATIO ON THE MAXIMUM AMPLITUDE

The normalized maximum amplitudes of the tuned bladed disks with a damping ratio of 0.01 decrease from 1 to 0.9 with the rate increasing from 0 to 20Hz/s, while the normalized maximum amplitudes of the mistuned bladed disks decrease from 2.05 to 1.8. When the damping ratio reduces to 0.005, the

normalized maximum amplitudes of the tuned bladed disks decrease from 1 to 0.7, and the normalized maximum amplitudes of the mistuned bladed disks decrease from 2.1 to 1.5. For damping ratio 0.003, the normalized maximum amplitude of the tuned bladed disk decreases from 1 to 0.5, and the normalized maximum amplitude of the mistuned bladed disks decreases from 2.1 to 1.2.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Effective methods for the forced response analysis of mistuned blade disks under complex excitation has been developed. The methods aimed at using the high-fidelity finite element models of bladed disks and reduced order techniques. An approach preserving the orthogonality and mass-normalization of the mode shapes is applied for accurate consideration the variation of modal characteristics with the rotation speed variation.

The methods have been developed for cases when the loading can be presented by arbitrary functions over time – without a need for mono- or multiharmonic expansion as in most previous studies. The analytical expressions of the time domain integrals required for periodic and transient analysis are derived, which reduces significantly the computational efforts compared with the traditional time-domain methods - for cases when the complex loading functions need to be considered.

The methods are verified on examples of analysis of tuned and mistuned lumped mass models. A realistic turbine bladed disk, comprising 86 sectors, is studied to demonstrate the mistuning effects on forced vibration responses of bladed disks. The influence of rotation speed on the steady-state periodic and transient forced response of mistuned bladed disks was analyzed, which proves the necessity of considering the influence of rotation speed.

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